

**«SPRING NO. 17», «SPRING NO. 18» IN GALLAOROL AND THEIR
PHYSICO-CHEMICAL ANALYZE RESULTS AND COMPARING WITH STATE
WATER QUALITY STANDARDS**

Tashpulatova Sabokhat Akbarovna¹

(PhD student)

Kamiljanova Shakhrizoda Akbarovna²

(Bachelor degree student)

Makhkamova Malika Akhror qizi³

(Bachelor degree student)

Khodiyeva Aziza Dilshod qizi⁴

(Bachelor degree student)

¹⁻²⁻³⁻⁴National University of Uzbekistan, Ecology Faculty, Uzbekistan

Tel: +99893 299 25 42;

E-mail: sabo_8728@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7098494>

Abstract: The spring water Spring No. 17, Spring No. 18 samples were examined by the analytical laboratory method, and the results of physical and chemical analysis of water, in particular, pH, SiO₂, dry residue, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Fe, CO₃²⁻, HCO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻, Cl, NO₂, NO₃, total hardness, K, indicators such as Na, Mn, Pb, Cu, Cr, Zn, Ni, Co, As, CNS, Al were determined. The results of chemical analysis were compared with the requirements of the national state standard for water quality and consumption.

Key words: Physico-chemical analysis, anthropogenic factor, Spring No. 17, Spring No. 18, Gallaorol district, Jizzakh region, Uzbekistan, State standards, water quality standard.

INTRODUCTION

Water is an important factor for human life and organism. Spring water is the main source of human needs. These two springs, which were sampled for chemical research, are located in the villages of Gallaorol District, Jizzakh Region, Uzbekistan. Almost all of the spring waters in the Gallaorol district meet the water needs of the population and are widely used for the purpose of irrigation of the farm, household and garden. Unfortunately, as a result of the human factor (anthropogenic influence) in recent years, spring waters are disappearing and their number is decreasing. Studying the physico-chemical composition of the water of Gallaorol springs allows for their rational use. And also, the results of this scientific research are not only important in preventing their disappearance, but also play an important role in using them as tourism, sacred religious destinations, as well as entertainment venues.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The object of research is the large springs in the villages of Gallaorol district of Jizzakh region in Uzbekistan. The springs in the Gallaorol region were conditionally named with numbers (Spring No. 17, Spring No. 18). Water samples from spring waters were placed in 1.5 liter polyethylene bottles, and their chemical analyzes was determined by a chemical analytical laboratory method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

These two springs (Spring No. 17 and Spring No. 18) are located in the villages of Gallaorol District, Jizzakh Region. Spring No.17, Spring No. 18 in Gallaorol district of Jizzakh region was studied. The results of the chemical analysis of the samples taken from these spring water are analyzed. The pH indicator of Spring No. 17 is 7, 4, which corresponds to the state standards of Uzbekistan (requirements for the quality of domestic and drinking water - 6.00-9.00), and it is weak alkaline. The SiO₂ indicator of spring water is 1.3 mg/dm³, and the indicator is suitable in the state standards. The dry residue of spring water is 302.1 mg/dm³, and the state standards state that it should be 1000.0-1500.00 mg/dm³, which means that it also meets the requirements for this indicator. The amount of Ca²⁺ from cations is 56.1 mg/dm³, the amount of Mg²⁺ is 14.6 mg/dm³, Fe - 0.05 mg/dm³, and meets state standards (0.3). From anions, CO₃²⁻ - <5, 0 mg/dm³, HCO₃⁻ - 158.6, SO₄²⁻ - 104.0 (400.00-500.00 by standard), Cl⁻ - 7.09 (250.00-350.00 by standard), NO₂⁻ - 0.01, NO₃⁻ - 25.8 mg/dm³ conforms to state standards (45.00). The total hardness of spring water is 3.9 mg-equiv/dm³, which suitable the standard requirements (7.00-10.00).

The pH indicator of Spring No. 18 is 7, 7, which corresponds to the state standards of Uzbekistan (requirements for the quality of domestic and drinking water - 6.00-9.00), and it is weak alkaline. The SiO₂ indicator of spring water is 2.1 mg/dm³, and the indicator is suitable in the state standards. The dry residue of spring water is 304.5 mg/dm³, and the state standards state that it should be 1000.0-1500.00 mg/dm³, which means that it also meets the requirements for this indicator. The amount of Ca²⁺ from cations is 60.1 mg/dm³, the amount of Mg²⁺ is 38.9 mg/dm³, Fe - 0.07 mg/dm³, and meets state standards (0.3). From anions, CO₃²⁻ - <5, 0 mg/dm³, HCO₃⁻ - 176.9, SO₄²⁻ - 60.4 (400.00-500.00 by standard), Cl⁻ - 17.7, (250.00-350.00 by standard), NO₂⁻ - 0.01, NO₃⁻ - 25.8 mg/dm³ conforms to state standards (45.00). The total hardness of spring water is 6.2 mg-equiv/dm³, which suitable the standard requirements (7.00-10.00).

Sampling process

A comparison of the results of chemical analysis of these two springs can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1.

Chemical analyze results of Spring No. 17 and Spring No. 18 (mg/dm³)

Spring name	pH	SiO ₂ mg/d m ³	Dry residue mg/dm ³	Ca ⁺ mg/d m ³	Mg ⁺ mg/d m ³	Fe mg/d m ³	CO ₃ ²⁻ mg/d m ³	HCO ₃ ⁻ mg/d m ³
Spring No. 17	7.4	1.3	302.1	56.1	14.6	0.05	<5.0	158.6
Spring No. 18	7.7	2.1	304.5	60.1	38.9	0.07	<5.0	176.9
State standards of Uzbekistan (UzDSt 951:2011)	6.0 - 9.0	---	1000.0 - 1500.0	---	---	0.3	---	---
State Standard of Uzbekistan	6.0 - 9.0	---	1000.0 - 1500.0	---	---	0.3	---	---

n (UzDSt
0950:201
1)

Spring name	SO ₄ ²⁻ mg/dm ³	Cl ⁻ mg/dm ³	NO ₂ ⁻ mg/dm ³	NO ₃ ⁻ mg/dm ³	Total hardness mg-equiv/dm ³
Spring No. 17	104.0	7.09	0.01	25.8	3.9
Spring No. 18	60.4	17.7	0.01	25.8	6.2
State standards of Uzbekistan (UzDSt 951:2011)	400.00-500.00	250.00-350.00	---	45.00	7.00-10.00

of
Uzbekistan
(UzDSt
951:2011)
State
Standard of
Uzbekistan
(UzDSt
0950:2011)

WOC
WORLD
ONLINE
CONFERENCES

The amount of K, Na, Mn, Pb, Cu, Cr, Zn, Ni, Co, As, CNS, Al was determined in the water of Spring No. 17 and Spring No. 18 (Table 2).

Table 2.

Chemical analysis results of Spring No. 17 and Spring No. 18 (mg/dm³)

Chemical analysis results of Spring No. 17

No.	Chemical element	mg/dm ³	No.	Chemical element	mg/dm ³
1	K	2,7	7	Zn	0,03
2	Na	29,6	8	Ni	0,09
3	Mn	<0,05	9	Co	0,38
4	Pb	<0,02	10	As	0,1
5	Cu	0,02	11	CNS	9,7
6	Cr	0,05	12	Al	<10,0

Chemical analysis results of Spring No. 18

No.	Chemical element	mg/dm ³	No.	Chemical element	mg/dm ³
1	K	2,2	7	Zn	0,03
2	Na	30,5	8	Ni	0,09
3	Mn	<0,05	9	Co	0,34
4	Pb	<0,02	10	As	0,1
5	Cu	0,02	11	CNS	9,7
6	Cr	0,05	12	Al	<10,0

Chemical analysis results (Table 2) Hygienic requirements and quality control for the supply of domestic drinking water to the state standards of Uzbekistan (UzDSt 951:2011) fully comply with the requirements of the State Standard of Uzbekistan, as well as drinking Hygienic requirements and quality control for drinking water fully comply with the requirements of the State Standard of Uzbekistan (UzDSt 0950:2011).

Acknowledgment

We express our gratitude to the Jizzakh regional "Hydrogeology" center, as well as to the water laboratory of the Navoi mining and metallurgical institute, which provided close assistance in the study and chemical analysis of springs in the Gallaorol region.

Conclusion

The results of chemical analysis were compared with the requirements of the national state standard for water quality and consumption. The results of the chemical analysis of spring water correspond to the requirements of the national standard of Uzbekistan (state standards for drinking and potable water).

References:

- [1]. Nesimović, E., Huremović, J.*, Gojak-Salimović, S., Avdić, N., Žero, S., Nesimović, E. Chemical Characterisation of the Spring Waters used for Health Care, Guber, Srebrenica, Bosnia and Herzegovina. Bulletin of the Chemists and Technologists of Bosnia and Herzegovina. 2017. Page 43.
- [2]. Dr. Syam Kumar Bariki. Physico-Chemical Quality of Some Spring Water Samples through Correlation Studies in Four Mandals of Tribal Area of Visakhapatnam District, Andhra Pradesh, India. Department of Environmental Sciences Andhra University, Visakhapatnam. International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Research (IJSER) ISSN (Online): 2347-3878 Index Copernicus Value (2015): 62.86 | Impact Factor (2015): 3.791. Page 33.

[3]. Bence Molnár and et al, Natural radioactivity and rock-water interactions in the springs of Sopron Mountains (Hungary). EGU22-10471 <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu22-10471> EGU General Assembly 2022 © Author(s) 2022. This work is distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License

[4]. S.A.Tashpulatova., A.D. Khodiyeva., Sh.A. Kamiljanova., M.A. Makhkamova «Chemical analyze results of «Spring No. 14», «Spring No. 15» and «Spring No. 16» in Gallaorol district in Jizzakh region in Uzbekistan». Academic Research in Modern Science. International Scientific-online Conference. 2022. September 22.

WOC
WORLD
ONLINE
CONFERENCES